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Dr. Shaifali Agrawal

Dr. Roopali Gupta

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HEALTH CARE DURING COVID -19

(with special reference to Literature)

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Abstract

Literature is the mirror of the society .All the shades of human beings are inside in it .we are living in the world of covid 19.where we can be able to get all human expressions with the help of literature. Covid 19 a pandemic disease has affected the whole world .Through this its a little effort to connect its rules with literature. Covid 19 all rules to protect ourself ,All these protective rules are represent in literature also. If we wants to see such types of examples in written form so it is easy to understand the concept easily through literature. In the public safety point of view few rules of covid 19 , has come from government .I am relating few of them with literature. For example wash hand, use mask social distance, and stay at home etc. . All these rules are still represent in literature. Government officially has given some instructions which are proving very effective for public health. They are just for the awareness of the public. . Different writers has written on such topics their views according to themselves.

Key Words – social ,health ,literature, rules, culture.

‘Literature is the artistic expression of thought which is replete with feeling and imagination according to Lord Marley ‘. In Literature consists of all the book where moral truth and human passion are touched with a certain largeness sanity and attraction of form.

In other words with literature heightens our Awareness of human life .It enables us to look at nature with new Eyes . These lines are showing clearly that literature is the mirror of the society whatever is happening in the society it covers all by it.It also expresses human feelings .It is just like the magical box where you are able to study human mind because different kinds of the characters their feelings ,whatever they are behaving that is inside this box. If literature is life so human beings are the sole .The word covid-19 this word is not new for us daily we’re listening about it through media posters radio . even common man also aware about it. After all health is wealth. Everyone is talking about this disease . We can judge this disease through these symptoms.

1. we can find out the symptoms of such kind of disease through fever ,dry cough , tiredness these are the common symptoms of coronavirus.

2.In this Stage rashes pain ,throat infection, conjunctivitis and the loss of Taste , skin problems can be seen, difficulty in breathing chest pain ,lack of strength, such type of symptoms can be very serious .

The condition of coronavirus has become very critical .Now we have more than 5 million confirmed cases of covid-19 up to May update 2020 around the World. yet this pandemic per series not the biggest ,but also in fact

the human Civilization the supplemental both have straight parallel run as humanity crisis. In our view this year 2020,21 has not only shown the worst side of humanity, In fact the doom side of humanity. which often has on noticed include destination country have blamed each other . W.H.O. Which has enough support to communities .Thanks to others , around the world to help ,on this critical situation.

Our honourable Prime Minister on 22nd March 2020 ,has announced new rules and regulations .so that we can be able to protect ourselves from this disease and we will be able to fight with this coronavirus virus . After all health has a very important part of our life. He has declared lock down on 22nd March .During the lock down here are some rules which has come for public. Which has to be followed by us. These rules are as follows - 1. wear a mask ,2. stay at their home , 3. very frequently and improve their immunity .so that we can be able to protect ourselves from this disease .All have to follow these rules and regulations very seriously . The guidelines for our health from the government every one has to obey. He announced that we have to live with Corona now because we have no medicine. so drink kadha in the connection of this, so many doctors and hospitals has also floated their rules . It has to be spread awareness in the society . so that we will be able to protect ourselves from this diseases. These rules we have to follow. For example

1. stay at home , 2. marks on your mouth ,3. social distancing , 4. increase immunity ,5. with postpone travel abroad for 2 years , 6. Wash your hands and legs when you come from the outside ,7 the threat of Corona is not going to be end very soon ,8. So people eat vegetarian food ,9. Do not go to unnecessary marriage and other ceremony 10th Be very careful while at barbershop, 11 Avoid shaking hands with others. These rules and regulations have changed our whole life. Our lifestyle has totally become changed. our society and culture that has also come in a critical position because everything has changed, our values tradition culture etc.

With the help of these rules I am just trying to connect them with literature. In literature such type of picture we can see easily .Therefore we can be able to see them through the eyes of literature to . Here I am going to connect few of them with literature. All these aspects have presented in Literature in such a way which has shown no difference between them. .Literature is just like the mirror of the society. Through literature its easy to understand what the condition of the corona in our life . Literature is just like a jewelry box where the different kinds of jewels so many characters, human expression ,related stories , and ,their nature have created new concept into this field.

All such kind of picture has already available in our literature. everybody has to follow rules and regulations. But the main cases have also still in front of us . The man as a literary human beings faced all

problem ,difficulties daily .only doctors ,police ,nurses , media person worked in their work place. They known as corona warriors .

This kind of disease corona has increased daily day by day ,so many days have passed still the condition has critically increased . Every one has to follow these rules. These rule we Can be able to see clearly with the help of 'Kitheen o Meares poem' 'Stay At Your Home .' In this poem we are also be able to see different types of rasa expressions .Through these rasa all the expressions of human beings can be seen in the connection of covid- 19 2020,21 For example _

1. Stay at your home _

stay at your home is one of the best poem by Kitheen o Meares . In this poem where she is trying to explain that stay at home ,with the help of this we are able to remove all our problems. We can connect it with the present situation of covid - 19 she is explaining from the very starting of the poems lines where she is saying 'and people stay at their home and read books and listen' we compare these lines with the present situation because everybody has to stay at their home. so it is quite clear to see that there is a close connection of the poem with present situation . Because all such kinds of activities all has to faced in the mid of covid-19 .we are doing everything in our home. we're staying at home due to the lockdown . we are unable to come out from home. Doing our work from home . Its a new concept which has developed now .There new revolution has come in our life from 22nd March 2020, when the Prime Minister Modi has announced the lock down.

In the lockdown everybody doctors, media, news, all are spreading the same kind of news they are requesting from there to stay home. so that the disease will not float very seriously all over the world. The new culture has developed now in our life, everybody is working from their home expect doctors, police, nurses, and media person because they are still working. They are Corona Warriors. otherwise those who are staying at their home they are working from their home through the online facility. so those who are not having any work they are still at there home. They are passing out their time through listening music, reading books and so many activities they are doing in the mid of Corona kal. Again the poet says in this poem that people are helping each Other. A new concept has developed. people have created new ways of life and heal the earth completely coronavirus infected our every part of life.

we all are hopeful about the coronavirus vaccine that it will come soon but still we have to wait for it. so many problems has created in the mid of the society. everybody is facing so many problems financially, mentally. Different shades of human nature has shown in these lines the poet is expressing very impressively in such a way - 'And created a new ways of life'

'And healed the earth completely' The poet in these line where she is saying that in the first everyone has to think with new vision some thing different because we have lost lot in our life. so don't think about the situation just do your work. just like where in Gita Lord Krishna is saying 'Karma Kiye Ja fal ki Ichha Mat Kar' through these lines our Lord Krishna says, that we only have to do our work and never think about the result. In lockdown people stayed at their home, read books, they are playing, dancing and doing their work regularly. But still they are in a psyche situation. In Corona kal common people special Children's and senior citizen they are very puzzled because government has strictly ordered for them that they are not able to come out from their home. The lines of this poem is giving a massage how to pass our time, so that negativity will not enter in our life. . She beautiful Express us everything in the poem.

2. Wash Your Hand -

We all have to wash our hands and legs psychologically all have changed their life style. This concept is clearly shown in Macbeth by Shakespeare. Lady Macbeth is saying that in 5 Act - "the Thane of fife had a wife where is she now? what will these hands never be cleaned? No more o., that my lord no more that you mar all with this starting'. Again Lady Macbeth says 'as psychic person where she is saying - 'the smell of blood is still, all the perfume of Arabia will not sweeten this little hand, in Macbeth the condition of Lady Macbeth after Duncan's murder become very serious through these speeches it is quite clear to show us, that so many time she is washing her hands and just to remove blood from her hand in this way 'all the perfumes of Arabia will not clean hands'. in the state of sanity she is behaving as a psychological person. Doctor also says 'this disease is beyond my practice' Lady Macbeth in such condition start walking at night. so many times. she has shown all these aspect in Shakespeare's Macbeth. This rule has shown so many times. especially Lady Macbeth is watching her hand so many times. in the same way just like a psyche figure, we are also doing the same kind of thing in our real life. If we compared that situation with the present one so we find that there is a similarity because we will not find any difference between them. that situation has come in our life. This point we can see in our life, we are washing our hand so many time because daily government is spreading the rules and regulation of Corona virus. even a small children's they have become habitual to wash their hands regularly and using sanitizer to. sometimes just like Lady Macbeth we also become irritate but our case is different because we have to fight against Corona virus at any cost. we have to take precaution very seriously and we have to obey all the instructions delivered and floating by our government. we are facing a new kind of disease even doctors don't know how to handle the situation. Even then they are paying their duties and working very hard day and night. They have become next to God during corona kal. They are the real fighter those who are fighting and attacking on coronavirus daily.

3. Avoid Shaking Hand -

The another rule not to shake hand other. AG Gardiner in his famous essay 'on shaking hand' speaking about the western culture the practice of greeting. On shaking hand in this essay the writer is saying so many times the

different kind of setting has not only the western but also the Indians are also behaving in the same way. They are also behaving same way. the president of USA Trump not only he in fact so many vvip dignities they are also accepting the tradition and the culture of India. they are accepting the value of Namaste in place of shaking hand. They are accepting to say Namaste in place of shaking hand. again Indian culture has proved itself in all over the world. there in this essay writer is trying to explain that in western countries this is their culture but in India it's a happy to say Namaste. whenever they need with other they have a shaking hand but during corona kal they have accepted to say Namaste because it is hygienic, in place of shaking hand. Because shaking head is unhygienic. in this Corona kal we have to accept this communication. say Namaste in place of shanking hand. The whole world is accepting the Indian culture they are saying Namaste, whenever they meet other in place of shaking hand and kissing each other. Now it has become a modern tradition. Universally Namaste has accepted.

4. Social distance -

Social distancing or do guj ki Dori through this rule we have to maintain social distance to take some precaution to stop this disease to spread. In this connection mysticism is the best example from which we can be able to take help to maintain a social distance. Now a days through the digital world we can able to connect ourself with God, and create a social distance. Evelyn Underhill says,

1. Mysticism is active and practical not passive and theoretical.
2. It's aims are wholly transcendental and spiritual the mystics heart is always set upon the changeless.
3. It has become a modern tradition. With this we can be able to maintain social distance also.
4. The virus also spread if we touch each other its a Union of top spiritually not physically.
5. Living Union with the one is a definite state or form of enhanced life.

Tagore is a mystical poet all his life he has maintained an ever growing and deep faith in God and sought to release the Oneness of a sole with the supreme soul of God. in Gitanjali mystical Outlook is there in 'clouds heap up on clouds' mystical devotional song. Tagore depicts the intense eternal Quest of the human soul to be united with the divine soul. it's just as a union of God and worked quickly not physically, like in this way.....
in the busy moment of noontide work I am with the Crowd but on the dark Lonely Day it is only for that I hope'. we have to maintain social distance in this way without giving pain to other this is the best source to give us relief from all the pain and sorrow and depression of a life. it is a easiest way to remove all the problems from our life. Its' the only way to control and defeat the pandemic disease. So make people follow social distance and also restrain them from moving out to avoid social connect.' mysticism is the best example to maintain social distance there is a union of God and mind but without any physical connection.

5. Wearing Mask—

In the connection of mask which is another main rule to protect yourself from corona. Different kinds of mask are available for different reasons. For example, The use of medical masks is advice if you have a direct fit respiratory symptoms coughing or sneezing to protect others if you don't have any symptoms then it's not necessary. Mask have used from the very earlier times. Few example are there which shows the impotence of mask.

1. To wear the mask according to 18th century the fashionable woman of London they were wearing masks. it was very popular for example is a 'Isabella reporting Mask frequently appear in 18th century. But the mid of 18th century, Fleet oval mask like the replicas, below left were being worm women not only to protect their identities and their modesty but also their complexion while riding on walking outdoors'. 'items sold an Etsy as mask and hand sanitizer, aren't medical grade. Etsy sellers can't make medical or great at ac sailors can't make Health claims'. So it was the tradition of that era. That's way they were using mask.

2. The surgical and procedures masks protect your clinical and you protect your patience. Cardinal health has a simplified surgical and procedure masks line that are all ASTM F2'00_11 rated. Such types of mask has used by medical staff for their safety point of view.

3. In Jainism they are also wearing masks. it is their tradition their culture they have some division in Jainism. which result in different practices followed nowadays both type of sentence with masks and without mask has some believe of not practices things which harm others . but they have to obey this to protect others discussed by Acharya's of deceit. according to the culture and time with fulfilment of ahimsa and other angle of Thinking before bringing and change. These examples are showing that during 18th century mask was in a fashion they were using masks just because of the passion and to protect their beauty. doctors use it to protect their self while they are in the touch of the patient .and Jain culture use it to protect themselves and not to harm others . during covid-19 it is the necessity to wear marks because government is floating this massages to wear mask . so that you will be able to protect yourself and others also . During covid-19 ,N 95 masks has become very popular . our honourable Prime Minister also announced to wear a handmade masks . it is safe also ,so you are able to wear homemade masks . With the help of these literary aspects are showing in corona kal or covid-19 . such Reflection is also showing in our daily life . most of us are facing so many problems because a new revolution has come in our life. society our cultural value has totally changed. our lifestyle has totally changed. we are using masks ,like Lady Macbeth we are washing our hand.

we are obeying all these rules and regulations ,using sanitizer also . For effectiveness factor as we are not going on any travelling, not doing any journey .In place of shaking hand and kissing we are accepting the importance of Namaste. once again we are accepting our old tradition and it is showing that old is gold. we are praying to God through the mystical outlook because mysticism is the easiest way to close ourselves to God and maintain social distance . you are able to pray God to remove such kind of situation, which we are facing . literature is a good source in our life in the mid of coronavirus case . It is the easiest way to understand the importance of rules and regulation through literally example. Its shows us the clear picture and we have to accept it. because time is flitting and art is long, in this critical situation we have to help ourselves and others to. The only way to fight against this situation that is , we have to take precaution for the safety point of others and ourselves to . covid-19 pandemic has delivered a strong and invaluable massage for all . Individual health is a concern for a single Nation in contrast and only Nation interest can transform into trouble for the entire.Finally on 16 Jan 2021 the vaccine has come. With the help of all these rules, all have to protected themselves. United we stand divided we fall . So 'Stand Together in solidarity and fight this pandemic for the most reliable way to protect and predict the future .' By Abraham Lincoln.

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